

Technologies for energy use of rice straw: a review

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Rice straw is a major field-based residue that is produced in large amounts in Asia. In fact, the total amount equaling 668 t could produce theoretically 187 gallons of bioethanol if the technology were available (Kim and Dale 2004). However, an increasing proportion of this rice straw undergoes field burning. This waste of energy seems inapt, given the high fuel prices and the great demand for reducing greenhouse gas emissions as well as air pollution. As climate change is extensively recognized as a threat to development, there is growing interest in alternative uses of field-based residues for energy applications. In contrast to the use of food crops (such as maize), the use of agricultural residues as biofuel offers a potential pathway of renewable energy that avoids risks for food security.

There are primarily two types of residues from rice cultivation that have potential in terms of energy—straw and husk. Although the technology of using rice husk is well established in many Asian countries, rice straw is, as of now, rarely used as a source of renewable energy. One of the principal reasons for the preferred use of husk is its easy procurement—that is, it is available at the rice mill. In the case of rice straw, however, its collection is laborious and its availability is limited to harvest time. The logistics of collection could be improved through baling, but the necessary equipment is expensive and buying it is uneconomical for most rice farmers. Thus, technologies for energy use

of straw must be especially efficient to compensate for the high costs involved in straw collection.

This review aims to give an overview of the available technologies for energy applications of rice straw, their development status, and the problems encountered in their use. It also provides an overview of rice straw quality as this property has an influence on technology efficiencies.

Rice straw quality

The chemical composition of feedstock has a major influence on the efficiency of bioenergy generation. Table 1 lists the chemical properties of rice straw, rice husk, and wheat straw to highlight the particular differences in feedstock. The low feedstock quality of rice straw is primarily determined by a high ash content (10–17%) as compared with wheat straw (around 3%) and also high silica content in ash (SiO_2 is 75% in rice and 55% in wheat) (Zevenhoven 2000). On the other hand, rice straw as feedstock has the advantage of having a relatively low total alkali content (Na_2O and K_2O typically comprise <15% of total ash), whereas wheat straw can typically have >25% alkali content in ash (Baxter et al 1996).

However, straw quality varies substantially within seasons as well as within regions. If straw is exposed to precipitation in the field, alkali and alkaline compounds are leached, improving the feedstock quality. In turn, moisture content should be <10% for combustion technology, which is the most mature technology at this point (see below). Rice husk also has poor feedstock quality, which is mainly caused by the very high silica content (Table 1), but its advantage is the uniformity in size. Thus, the preferred use of this material for bioenergy is related to both quality and availability.

Table 1. Proximate composition and selected major elements of ash in rice straw, rice husk, and wheat straw.

	Rice straw	Rice husk	Wheat straw
Proximate analysis (% dry fuel)			
Fixed carbon	15.86	16.22	17.71
Volatile matter	65.47	63.52	75.27
Ash	18.67	20.26	7.02
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00
Elemental composition of ash (%)			
SiO_2	74.67	91.42	55.32
CaO	3.01	3.21	6.14
MgO	1.75	<0.01	1.06
Na_2O	0.96	0.21	1.71
K_2O	12.30	3.71	25.60

Source: Jenkins et al (1998).

Energy technologies

The transportation of biomass is one of the key cost factors for its use as a source of renewable energy. Decentralized energy systems provide an opportunity to use biomass to meet local energy requirements—that is, heat and electricity. In contrast to straw, the use of rice husk for energy has been realized faster. One important factor is that rice mills can use the husk to serve their internal energy requirement. As an alternative, rice millers could sell the husk to a power-plant operator. The propagation of rice husk use for energy was accelerated by energy providers, who deal with a relatively small number of rice millers for supplying husk, which is an easier task than dealing with thousands of farmers supplying rice straw. As a new trend, electricity is now often produced by the millers themselves and then sold to a power grid. This setup has to be seen as the most promising option in terms of logistics and transportation energy saved.

Transportation costs of straw are a major constraint to its use as an energy source. As a rule of thumb, transportation distances beyond a 25–50-km radius (depending on local infrastructure) are uneconomical. For long distances, straw could be compressed as bales or briquettes in the field, rendering transport to the site of use a viable option. Nevertheless, the logistics of a supply chain is more complicated in the case of straw.

Although five different energy conversion technologies seem to be applicable for rice straw in principle (Fig. 1), only combustion technology is currently commercialized and the other technologies are at different stages of development.

As a general rule for energy use, each step in the chain consumes a certain amount of energy and thus reduces the net energy of the end product.

The following sections describe the principal features of the possible energy conversion technologies, experiences, and technical difficulties in the use of rice straw.

Thermal combustion

Rice straw can either be used alone or mixed with other biomass materials (the latter is called co-firing or co-combustion) in direct combustion. In this technology, combustion boilers are used in combination with steam turbines to produce electricity and heat. The energy content of rice straw is around 14 MJ kg^{-1} at a moisture content of 10% (EEF 2007). In thermal combustion, air is injected into the combustion chamber to ensure that the biomass is completely burned in the combustion chamber.

Fig. 1. Energy conversion technologies for rice straw.

Fluidized bed technology is one of the direct combustion techniques in which solid fuel is burned in suspension by forced air supply into the combustion chamber to achieve complete combustion. A proper air-to-fuel ratio is maintained and, in the absence of a sufficient air supply, boiler operation encounters various problems.

In straw combustion at high temperatures, potassium is transformed and combines with other alkali earth materials such as calcium. This in turn reacts with silicates, leading to the formation of tightly sintered structures on the grates and at the furnace wall. Alkali earths are also important in the formation of slags and deposits. This means that fuels with lower alkali content are less problematic when fired in a boiler (Jenkins et al 1998). The by-products are fly ash and bottom ash, which have an economic value and could be used in cement and/or brick manufacturing, construction of roads and embankments, etc.

Experiences with existing facilities in India, China, and Europe are described in detail in Annex 1. The following is a summary of the technical difficulties and measures adapted to overcome these constraints.

1. The alkali content of straw (both wheat and rice) is high and these compounds have the typical characteristic of melting at comparatively low temperatures and forming alkali deposits (Miles et al 1995). The measure adapted is to increase the melting point of ash through the addition of limestone. This indirectly reduces sulfur (especially SO_2) emissions as well.
2. The high alkali content of straw at high temperature results in increased corrosion and fouling problems in the superheater (Barnes 1999). Although this problem cannot be avoided completely, its adverse effects can be mitigated through controlled boiler temperature and special coating on the superheater surface. In addition, as mentioned earlier, alkali and alkaline compounds are leached when straw is exposed to precipitation in the field. This improves feedstock quality by increasing the melting temperature of ash (Jenkins et al 1998).
3. The silica content of rice straw ash is around 75%, which has a low melting point. In addition to feeding limestone onto the furnace bed, controlling the temperatures inside the boiler is essential to prevent the melting of silicon dioxide (SiO_2).

The quality of by-product may not be good if straw is co-fired in coal power plants—that is, the ash may not be suitable for cement manufacturing.

Carbonization

Carbonization is one of the thermal conversion techniques wherein charcoal (process output) is produced by heating the carbonaceous fuel under restricted air flow. But this process releases environmentally harmful emissions. A good-quality charcoal could be obtained in a kiln when its temperature is maintained around 450–500 °C. In the best case, the charcoal can have a carbon content of more than 70%, a volatile element content of 25% or lower, and ash could be around 5% (Wereko-Brobby and Hagen 1996).

Carbonization could be an alternative to open-field burning in locations where straw transport is not economical and the point of use is more than 50 km away. When rice straw undergoes carbonization, the product is char, often called biochar. This may have a lower carbon percentage when the rice straw has high ash content (10–17%). Biochar can then be incorporated into the soil to act as a soil conditioner by improving the structure and fertility of the soil as well as a carbon sink because the carbon is stabilized in the char (Lehmann 2007b). But, before doing so, the carbon emission balance needs to be estimated for the carbonization process and open-field burning to ensure how much carbon is stabilized through carbonization.

There are experiences with sugarcane trash at the field level. This is also a low-density material and, after carbonization, the powdery char is mixed with a suitable binder and shaped with the help of a mold into briquettes. The briquettes are then dried under the sun before being used as fuel (ARTI 2007). The possibility of using rice straw in a similar way cannot be ruled out as it is also a major field-based residue.

Pyrolysis

This technology is one of the thermo-chemical conversion methods by which carbonaceous fuel can be readily converted into gas, liquid, char, or a combination of these three. Pyrolysis is the process in which biomass is heated in the absence of air to around 500 °C. The rate of change in process temperature and process duration guides the composition of gas and char that could be varied. The slow pyrolysis enhances char production, which is a transfer to the stable form of carbon, and the

higher concentration of lignin increases carbon recovery (Lehmann 2007a). In this regard, rice straw is a potential feedstock as its lignin content is 22.3% (hemicellulose—35.7%, cellulose—32.0%, and extractive matter—10%) (Worasuwannarak et al 2007). Fast pyrolysis is practiced to enhance liquid production (i.e., bio-oil). The by-products of the pyrolysis process (liquid and gas) are used to meet the energy requirements of the process or eventually to produce surplus energy. From that perspective, even char could be used as a fuel. The pyrolysis process needs an external heating source—it could be the gases evolved during the process itself. Use of the gases that evolved during pyrolysis improves the energy balance as well as the carbon balance, but this analysis has never been reported recently for the feedstock under consideration. This technology is still in an R&D phase.

Experimental results show that pyrolysis temperature and atmosphere have an influence on bio-oil yield and composition, for which particle size has a minor influence on product yields (Putun et al 2004). The optimal conditions for maximizing bio-oil yield are a maximum temperature of 550 °C with a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹ and particle size between 0.850 mm and 8.425 mm. Use of an inert gas as sweeping gas atmosphere increases bio-oil yield significantly, whereas the yield of char and gas reduces it (Calvo et al 2004). Worasuwanarak et al (2007) observed a difference in gas formation during pyrolysis of different types of biomass and this was attributed to the composition of hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin. The large amount of water production during pyrolysis of rice straw was thought to be caused by its high hemicellulose content (Worasuwannarak et al 2007).

A different approach was followed by Antonietti (2006) in the production of biochar. Biomass and water were placed in a pressure container and a catalyst was added. This mixture is heated up to 180 °C in the absence of air. After 12 h, the mixture was allowed to cool. The output is a black powder consisting of coal nanospheres (Antonietti 2006). It is too early to comment on this technology as it is currently in the R&D stage. In addition, there has to be an analysis of the energy and carbon balance for this process.

Many data are not available with regard to pre-processing required for rice straw pyrolysis. However, being a low-density material, rice straw needs briquetting if the product of pyrolysis is char.

Gasification

Gasification is a thermo-chemical conversion method, in which solid biomass is directly converted into gas. It requires high temperatures (about 700 °C) with a controlled amount of air or oxygen to a gaseous mixture, which is called synthesis gas or syngas. Rice straw could be used directly in a gasifier along with other biomass materials to produce syngas. Syngas could be used in an internal combustion (IC) engine to produce electricity or in a combined heat and power (CHP) plant to produce electricity as well as heat. Although the experiments so far were performed with wheat straw (which has low ash content), a similar behavior is expected in the case of rice straw. In Thailand, rice husk is being used successfully in a fluidized bed gasifier and after gas cleanup is fed to the IC engines. However, problems persist due to tar content in the cleaned syngas.

To overcome the technical difficulties in the energy use of wheat straw, the Technical University of Denmark (DTU), along with other partners, identified a new method to gasify straw in a low-temperature circulating fluidized bed (LT-CFB) gasifier and the produced gas is fed into direct combustion boilers (DEA 2003, Stoholm et al 1999). Another technique tested in the 1990s at DTU used a 50-kW system combined with an initial step of straw pyrolysis. The char and volatile pyrolysis products passed to the top of a gasifier for combustion. This technique tremendously reduced the tar content of syngas (nearly tar-free gas) (Henriksen and Christensen 1994). This new gasification technique could provide an opportunity for the efficient use of difficult biomass materials such as rice straw.

To summarize the technology experiences with wheat straw in Europe, problems similar to those seen in combustion are likewise observed in gasification, especially the formation of alkali deposits and ash melting. Measures to overcome the technical hurdle could be either softened and melted ashes can be handled or the maximum temperature in the gasifier can be kept below the softening point of ash (Henriksen and Christensen 1994).

In addition, other approaches exist combining gasification and production of liquid fuels using, for example, Fisher-Tropsch synthesis. This process is called biomass to liquid (BtL).

Biomethanation

This is a bio-conversion technique wherein rice straw could be used alone or mixed with municipi-

pal/industrial solid waste or liquid waste (biodegradable) and fed into bioreactors. When mixed with other biodegradable material, the straw acts as a buffer to control pH as well as degradation of cellulose material, which leads to the production of biogas. Biogas could be used directly in IC engines or CHP systems to produce electricity and heat. Since 2003-04, the Sardar Patel Renewable Energy Research Institute (SPRERI) has been conducting research on a 100 kg d⁻¹ rice straw-based biomethanation system in both mesophilic and thermophilic digestion. Biogas yield is higher in thermophilic digestion than in mesophilic digestion, around 340 L kg⁻¹ of total solids (SPRERI 2006). The biogas yield achieved in mesophilic digestion is around 233 L kg⁻¹ of dry matter added (biogas calorific value is 6–6.5 kWh m⁻³) at a C-N ratio of 30:1 with maximum volatile solid degradation of around 56% (Bardiya and Gaur 1997).

A consistent feed of biomass is expected in the digester every day to maintain steady microbial activity. In addition, pH and temperature need to be controlled for effective microbial activity. As rice straw is usually a dry resource and would contain only limited digestible substances (very high C-N ratio, could vary up to 75% [Zhu 2007]), it alone is a bad substrate.

As the technology is in the R&D stage, data pertaining to possible commercial capacity and its economics are not available.

Hydrolysis followed by fermentation

In California, several companies work on the biological conversion of rice straw (lignocellulosic material) to ethanol. The Colusa Biomass Energy Corporation (CBEC) is one such company working toward an integrated bio-refinery concept, which could produce approximately 143,000 L of ethanol daily. This process is now patented. The rice straw is hydrolyzed first using enzymes (some would adopt acid or base); it is then fermented to produce ethanol (CBEC 2007).

In this process, good yields of ethanol are known to be produced (303–379 L t⁻¹ of rice straw). The ash and silica are co-products for which commercial markets are being evaluated (Schuetzle 2006). As per Karimi et al (2006), 1 kg of rice straw will contain 390 g of cellulose. This amount of cellulose is theoretically enough to produce 220 g or 283 mL of ethanol. However, considering the practically achievable best yield as 74%, it could produce 208 mL of ethanol from a cellulose content of 1 kg of rice straw (Karimi et al 2006). Honda, a leading car manufacturer, envi-

sions that the future generation of cars would run on leaves and rice straw (MarketWatch 2006). Many research institutions and organizations are working on this technology across the world (Schuetzle 2006, Anonymous, no date).

Still, the challenge is for cost-effective pretreatment of rice straw. This pretreatment requires shredding, steam explosion, and enzyme treatment of rice straw. Nevertheless, much information is not known in the public domain as most of the processes developed are patented.

Summary of energy technologies for rice straw

The results of the evaluation of technologies are summarized in Table 2, with different parameters indicated. The main findings are as follows:

- Combustion technology is well established and power plants in the range of 5–12 MW are possible in decentralized locations where the density of rice straw produced is high. Although there are system capacities up to 24 MW, fuel security would be an issue.
- In very remote locations where transporting rice straw over longer distances is quite challenging, farmers could adopt a technique that is easier to be practiced in the field. In this regard, carbonization seems a viable solution. However, a carbon emission balance analysis needs to be done in comparison with open-field burning of rice straw and other possible options, if there are any.
- Although gasification of rice husk is proven, the problems associated with the tar content in syngas and ash melting are unavoidable. Hence, a combination of pyrolysis, followed by gasification, seems to work better for rice straw. However, further research on the use of rice straw in pyrolysis and gasification is needed.
- Because of the low energy density of biomethanation technology as well as the low bulk density of rice straw, thermophilic digestion has an advantage over mesophilic digestion. However, this technology is still in the R&D phase.
- Although the demand for liquid fuel is high and extensive research is now under way in the conversion of lignocellulosic material to liquid fuel, the challenge is still achieving cost-effective pretreatment of rice straw for ethanol production.

Conclusions

It is possible to use rice straw for energy applications, although technical difficulties exist in using

rice straw for direct combustion technology. Nevertheless, these could be overcome through additional measures. Still, the challenge is in the sourcing of rice straw required for continued plant operation—that is, logistical aspects. Thus, co-combustion has a better opportunity for the use of rice straw. The biomethanation technology is still in the R&D phase and economic aspects are not yet known. The lasting application of rice straw use for energy could never be successful unless logistics are worked out well. Otherwise, theoretical estimates on energy production would remain a dream.

The pragmatic approach would be to develop application-specific technology solutions, such as, if a surplus quantity of rice straw exists in a given area within a 25–50-km radius, direct combustion, provided the rice straw is baled in the field before transport. There are successful examples in a few Asian countries where baling of rice straw is practiced to transport rice straw for other applications. Or, a technology such as carbonization could be implemented at a small scale. There is a need for thorough research to evaluate whether applying biochar or charcoal onto the soil is more beneficial than using it as energy sources. As biochar or charcoal would have an energy content of about 30 MJ kg⁻¹, further analysis of the energy and carbon balance is required. From combustion technology, it is apparent that there are additional operation (collection and transportation) and maintenance (addition of lime, running at lower efficiency) costs involved. Hence, governments should provide continuous support, through policies for successful demonstration and financial incentives to cover the risks, when rice straw is used for energy applications.

By having these measures in place, governments could convince farmers not to burn rice straw and enforce environmental regulations on open-field residue burning.

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Table 2. Summary of technologies.

Parameter	Technologies				
	Thermal combustion	Pyrolysis (fast and slow)	Gasification	Biomethanation	Hydrolysis followed by fermentation
Form of energy output	Electricity	Bio-oil or and/or heat	Syngas charcoal	Biogas	Ethanol
Mode of operation	Centralized	Decentralized and decentralized	Decentralized	Decentralized	Centralized
Applications	Large and commercialized, connected to electricity grid	Small-scale production of charcoal	Energy needs of a small Industry or a few hundred houses	Energy needs of less than 100 houses	Replacement of fossil fuel such as petrol and diesel for automobile
Stage of development	Commercialized	R&D	R&D	Being practiced at a small scale	Beginning phase; R&D
Capacity of output range of existing systems	Up to 10 MW	Few liters of liquid or kg of solid fuel	Up to 1 MW	Few kW range	Tons or liters of liquid
Processing of rice straw as feedstock	Baling	For charcoal-briquetting; for bio-oil-pulverizing or grinding	Should be briquetted	As received	Basic preparation—perhaps shredding
Overall efficiency of the system	Around 20%	Not yet known	Around 20–25%	Not yet known	Not yet known
Straw consumption	1.4 kg kWh ⁻¹	Not yet known	1.1–1.5 kg kWh ⁻¹	Few kg at a certain rate on a daily basis	Not yet known
Operation and maintenance cost	Competing with current price	Moderate	Moderate to high	Competing with current price	Very high
Levelized cost a (€cents/kWh _{el})—2010	11–13 (SE-cogen.)	Moderate	Moderate	8 (biowaste-IC engine 500 kW)	Very high
Jobs created * (persons/TWh _{el})	370–390	Not yet known	Not yet known	522	Not yet known
Net savings in terms of GHG _{eq}	Very high	Moderate	Above moderate	Low	Very high

*Fritsche UR. 2005. Öko-Institut (Institute for Applied Ecology), Darmstadt Office, applicable wherever values are mentioned.

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Annex 1. Experiences with existing facilities

Development status and lessons from existing facilities in India

A 10-MW power plant, which used rice straw as fuel, was constructed at Jalkheri village in Punjab State by the Punjab State Electricity Board (PSEB) in 1992. This was the first plant of its kind using “fluidized bed” technology (the boiler was supplied by Bharat Heavy Electricals Limited) for firing rice straw. Rice straw bales were dropped into the fluidized bed combustion chamber, which weighs around 15–18 kg, and this created difficulties in fluidization in the boiler. Rice straw ash has a very low melting point, and this requires maintaining the boiler temperature below the ash melting temperature. The ash, composed of sodium, potassium, magnesium, and silica, has created innumerable problems such as ash melting, slagging, superheater choking, and clinker formation. The inconsistency in boiler temperature was due to the moisture in the bales. Initially, the plant was operated for only 15 d continuously and then it was shut down.

Later, some of these problems were overcome through the addition of limestone into a free board, just above the boiler bed level (Muthukrishnan et al 1995), as well as by sheltering the fuel required for a few days of operation. Despite this, the plant could not be operated on a sustained basis because of fuel insecurity. The plant was shut down for 8 years before it was brought back into operation in 2002. Again, during this period, fuel security was a major issue on top of problems with the conveyor system. In 2004, investment was made to set up a new feeding system capable of feeding various biomass fuels.

The experience drawn from this plant indicates that rice straw alone could be used in the combustion (5–12 MW range), but it has many operational problems. The Ministry of New and Renewable Energy, Government of India, has given the go signal for the implementation of rice straw-based power plants. Nine plants (12 MW each) in Punjab and eight (12 MW each) in Haryana totaled 204 MWel (Anonymous 2006). The first plant at Ghannur, Punjab, is expected to be operational by October 2008, which could use other biomass fuels as well. But the primary focus is the use of rice straw.

Development status in China

Six power projects are being implemented in Jiangsu Province, China. One project has started operation,

supplying electricity to the East China Power Grid (JGRBG 2007).

The Zhongjieneng Suqian (2 × 12 MW) biomass power project located in the southeastern part of Suqian City, northwest of Jiangsu Province, has been operational since March 2007. This plant uses wheat and rice residues generated in the vicinity of Suqian City. The total amount of biomass residue generated in this region is around 1,690,000 t annually within the 25-km radial distance from the plant site. A maximum of 195,000 t of biomass will be used in the power plant. The Zhongjieneng Jurong (2 × 12 MW) biomass power project is located near Daijia village, Huayang town, Jurong City in southern Jiangsu. These two plants are equipped with a circulating fluidized bed (CFB) boiler. They are designed to handle various types of biomass resources. At least 50–60% of the biomass expected to be used in these plants is rice straw.

The Jiangsu Rudong Biomass Power Generation Project (25 MW) is now under way in Rudong County, Jiangsu Province. This plant will source the available straw (mainly rice straw, wheat straw, and maize straw) within a 50-km radius of the power plant site and the maximum straw consumption is approximately 150,000 t per year (about 60% of this is rice straw). The project is expected to be operational in March 2008. The straw-fired power plant consists of one 110 t h⁻¹ high-temperature, high-pressure, straw-fired boiler (the boiler was supplied by Wuxi Huaguang Boiler Co., Ltd.) and one 25-MW generator unit. Other projects are under way at three locations: Sheyang (25 MW), Donghai (2 × 12 MW), and Huaian (2 × 15 MW) (JGRBG 2007).

All these projects are in Jiangsu and care has been taken toward fuel security and collection and transportation to the project site or closest collection point. Safety standards have been tightened at storage sites as straw could catch fire easily. It is assumed that collection and transportation charges will increase every year because of increasing labor and transport costs.

Lessons from existing facilities in Europe with wheat straw

Denmark has played a pioneering role in the co-combustion of biomass (especially wheat straw) since the 1970s. Denmark has 75 straw-fired plants and about 11 of these are combined heat and power (CHP) plants (IEA/OECD 2002) wherein wheat straw alone is used or co-combusted. As the name implies, a CHP plant generates heat as

well as electricity. As of 2000, Denmark, Sweden, and the United Kingdom were the only countries using straw in total primary energy consumption (Alakangas and Vesterinen 2003). However, several countries in Europe are using straw for decentralized heating applications.

In Denmark, the companies MidtKraft and ELSAMPROJEKT have worked on the co-combustion of coal and wheat straw in CFB boilers since 1988 with pilot combustion tests. The technical difficulties are similar to those observed in the Indian plants. Additional problems were derived from seasonal differences in the composition of straw

due to its exposure to precipitation (Rasmussen and Clausen 1994). However, over a decade of extensive research, the average efficiency of a straw-fired steam turbine plant has been raised from 20–25% to 25–32% in small plants, whereas the more advanced and larger power plants can now reach efficiencies of 42–50% (DEA 2003). One example of a district heating system in Denmark is the Sydlangeland district heating plant, which was built in 1993. This system produces approximately 30,000 MWh of heat a year and is equipped with two boilers—a 5-MW straw-fired boiler and a 6-MW oil-fired boiler.

